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The moth fly *Clogmia albipunctata* (Diptera: Psychodidae) in Ukraine

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Oboňa, J., Ježek, J., Fogašová, K., Manko, P. & Korneyev, V.A. The moth fly *Clogmia albipunctata* (Diptera: Psychodidae) in Ukraine. — The moth midge *Clogmia albipunctata* (Williston, 1893), one of the largest moth flies, living as larvae in sink and toilet pipes (“drainage worms”) is an alien species expanding in Europe. Despite its epidemiological and ecological significance, this species escaped from the attention of entomologists. This work provides the first information about its occurrence in Ukraine based on data obtained from iNaturalist and UkrBIN sites.

Key words: Diptera, Psychodidae, moth flies, drain worms, iNaturalist, UkrBIN, invasive species.

Обоња, Й., Єжек, Я., Фогашова, К., Манько, П. і Корнєєв, В.О. Метеликівка *Clogmia albipunctata* (Diptera: Psychodidae) в Україні. — Метеликівка *Clogmia albipunctata* (Williston, 1893), одна з найбільших метеликівок, що живе у на личинковій стадії в раковинах та унітазах («трубні черви») — чужорідний вид, який поширюється в Європі. Незважаючи на своє епідеміологічне та екологічне значення, цей вид залишився поза увагою ентомологів. У цій роботі наведено першу інформацію про його появу в Україні на основі даних, отриманих із сайтів iNaturalist та UkrBIN.

Ключові слова: двокрили, Psychodidae, метеликівки, трубні черви, iNaturalist, UkrBIN, інвазійні види.

Introduction

Clogmia albipunctata (Williston, 1893) (Diptera: Psychodidae) (Figs 1–2) is an expansive, often synanthropic moth midge species alien for Europe, originally described from Cuba and previously known to occur circumtropically and circumsubtropically (e.g., Wagner, 1990; Ježek & Goutner, 1995; Oboňa & Ježek, 2012; Humala & Polevoi, 2015; Afzan & Belqat, 2016; Bejarano & Estrada, 2016; Cazorla-Perfetti & Moreno, 2017; Trájer & Juhász, 2017; Ježek *et al.*, 2018; Cazorla-Perfetti, 2019; Oboňa *et al.*, 2019; Salmela *et al.*, 2019; Zित्रа *et al.*, 2020; Morelli & Biscaccianti, 2021). Its larvae develop in sewer drains, plant pots, swamps, etc. This midge is known as a causal agent of urinary and gastrointestinal myiasis (Farrag *et al.*, 2019; Geremy-Depatureaux *et al.*, 2019; Gökçe, 2020), and is capable to spread multidrug-resistant bacteria from wastewater systems (Rupprecht *et al.*, 2020).

It is a large moth fly (wing 3–5 mm), which can be readily recognised from its predominantly dark setulae on

body and wings, with patterns of 7–8 bright white costal spots (“stars”) and less expressed pair of white and pair of darker spots in the wing disk (Figs 1–2) in females, which can be identified even on photographs. Its occurrence in Ukraine has not been recorded on the FaunaEuropaea site (Wagner, 2013) nor published elsewhere in the literature. Due to its frequent occurrence in human dwellings, it is therefore very important to pay sufficient attention to it.

Material and methods

Data presented in this paper comes from iNaturalist (2020) and UkrBIN (2021), where all photos of the family Psychodidae recorded in Ukraine, and of them those with reliable species identification were selected.

From each data verified in this way (data list contains the following information: locality, coordinates, date, observer (and link to the iNaturalist or UkrBIN record –

Figs 1–2. *Clogmia albipunctata* (photos by Matej Žiak and Mykola Borysenko, respectively).

accessed 11.12.2020 / 7.10.2021) the geographical location of the record, decimal coordinates and data of observation were extracted, which was then transferred to the maps (Figs 3–4).

Clogmia albipunctata (Williston, 1893)

Synonymy. *Clogmia albipunctatus* (Williston, 1893); *Psychoda albipunctatus* Williston, 1893; *Psychoda nigrithorax* Abreu, 1930; *Psychoda nocturna* Abreu, 1930; *Telmatoscopus haranti* Mirouse, 1958.

Data list

2018: Donetsk Region, Kostyantynivka, 48.521862 37.737637, 15.11.2018 (naturalist5244) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/18414198>).

2019: Cherkaska Region, Zolotonosha District, 49.675600 32.038037, 23.08.2019 (Mykola Borysenko)

Crimea, Feodosija, 45.032936 35.374023, 30.09.2019 (lenatara) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/31776169>);

Crimea, Klepyne, 45.52754 34.18748, 22.09.2019 (talyat) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/31272527>);

Lviv City, [49.822 24.075], 08.09.2019 (Zahorodnyi Ivan) (https://ukrbin.com/show_image.php?imageid=129907);

Odesa, 46.487308 30.742078, 11.08.2019 (tapaculo99) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/30635345>);

Odeska Region, Kryzhanivka, 46.558931 30.787728, 13.07.2019 (yuliia_spinova) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/49366961>).

2020: Crimea, Olenivka, 45.383873 32.506637, 27.07.2020 (melodi_96) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/61584263>);

Crimea, Olenivka, 45.384623 32.505772, 23.06.2020 (melodi_96) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/54190143>);

Crimea, Simferopol, 44.919784 34.084548, 23.07.2020 (vladikaladik228) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/54039731>);

Crimea, Sudak, 44.847672 34.993011, 15.09.2020 (vovanatur) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/59705298>);

Crimea, Yantarne, 45.420125 34.287396, 29.08.2020 (denis_m) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/59047918>);

Dnipropetrovska Region, Dnipro District, 48.352056 35.016569, 19.09.2020 (Vika Roi) (https://ukrbin.com/show_image.php?imageid=179882);

Kyiv env, 50.427637 30.494249, 26.07.2020 (aleksandr_levon) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/54451191>);

Kyiv env, 50.49084 30.408416, 29.07.2020 (igor117) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/54733079>);

Kyiv env., 50.448383 30.624806 21.07.2020 (yuliia_spinova) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/54507911>);

Kyiv Region, Vasylykiv, 50.177089 30.319638, 3.06.2020 (julia_naumovich) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/58416046>);

Kyiv Region, Vyshneve env, 50.365373 30.449614, 4.09.2020 (stas_golodryga) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/58487133>);

Mykolaiv, 46.983221 32.000756, 23.06.2020 (efarilis) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/50692029>); the same, 46.983221 32.000756, 2.10.2020, efarilis) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/61482509>);

Odeska Region, Chornomorsk, 46.405995 30.736192, 26.05.2020 (tanya34217) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/47400265>);

Rivnenska Region, Bohdashiv, 50.525053 26.243504, 3.09.2020 (aleksandr_levon) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/58446555>);

Zakarpatska Region, Vynohradiv District, 48.151985 23.127753, 14.09.2020 (Vasyl Hleba (basileus)) (https://ukrbin.com/show_image.php?imageid=177763);

Zaporozhia, 47.822759 35.170234 28.09.2020 (aleksandr_levon) (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/61132266>).

Results and discussion

The oldest verified record of the species *C. albipunctata* from Ukraine became from 2018 (only one record). From the following year 2019 another 4 and in 2020 another 16 records were found in iNaturalist (Fig. 2). These data suggest the beginning of the expansion of *C.*

Figs 3–4. Records of *Clogmia albipunctata* in 2018–2020 in Ukraine obtained from the iNaturalist (Fig. 3) and UkrBIN (Fig. 4).

albipunctata into the territory of Ukraine. In the next year is expected further growth. The number of known species of Psychodidae family in Ukraine is elevated from 43 (Ježek *et al.*, 2017) to 44 by the records of *C. albipunctata*.

The obtained data suggest that the colonization of Ukraine may have started from the east (2018) and the south (2019). Currently, populations are believed to be present, especially in large cities as Kyiv (frequentmost observations), Lviv, Rivne, Dnipro (Dnepropetrovsk), Odesa, and Mykolaiv.

The impact of this species to native species is not yet entirely clear, but it is thought to pose a threat, especially to local synanthropic species. For its mass occurrence in human dwellings (bathrooms and toilets) sufficient attention must be paid to this species.

Observations from iNaturalist could be used not only for species monitoring and for detection of specific diseases and/or pests (Rossi, 2017). Especially for easily identifiable species, iNaturalist can provide a suitable information base for applied research.

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